

Schrodinger Equation Without Explicit Plane Wave Exp(ipx)?

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Quantum mechanics often begins with a wavefunction, which is strongly tied to the form of a plane wave i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. For example, a free particle with momentum p has a wavefunction of $\exp(ipx)$. A bound particle has a real wavefunction $W(x)$ which may be written as $\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$ where each $\exp(ipx)$ has the physical meaning of a free particle wavefunction. In addition, the average kinetic energy is given in terms of an average involving $\exp(ipx)$ which seems a little unusual:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \left(\sum_p p^2/2m f_p \exp(ipx) \right) / \left(\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx) \right) + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

If one, however, considers $x=0$ and moves to $x=dx$, where dx is infinitesimal, it seems the form $\exp(ipx)$ disappears. In such a case, one may calculate kinetic energy at $x=0$ based on an average of different $p^2/2m$ with normalized weights f_p . (These weights may be positive or negative, because kinetic energy may be 0 at $x=0$.) If it were possible to devise a function based on a flux of $p^2/2m$, one might be able to describe how average kinetic energy changes from $x=0$ to $x=dx$. From this, one might derive the form of $\exp(ipx)$.

Average Kinetic Energy and Flux

In quantum mechanics, the probability of a momentum state p is $f_p \cdot f_p$. This does not involve x at all. It is known, however, from the Schrodinger equation that average kinetic energy at x is given by ((1)). In ((1)) f_p as well as $\exp(ipx)$ are used as weights. If one sets $x=0$ in ((1)), the average kinetic energy at $x=0$ should be:

$$KE(x=0) = \left(\sum_p p^2/2m f_p \right) / \left(\sum_p f_p \right) \quad ((2))$$

For the sake of argument, consider $f_p = -f_{-p}$, i.e. f_p is odd in p . Furthermore, f_p could be negative because it is possible the kinetic energy is 0 at $x=0$ if $V(x=0)=E$. In ((2)), there is no appearance of an $\exp(ipx)$.

From classical conservation of energy, it is known that $KE(x=0)$ is not the same as $KE(x=dx)$. Thus, somehow, there is an increase in kinetic energy from $x=0$ to $x=dx$. There is no acceleration, however, of the p values, but in general the weights $f(p,x)$ may change from point to point, giving the appearance of an acceleration. At $x=0$, however, no x is present, so one should be able to describe a flux of kinetic energy based solely on f_p and p .

In order to determine what this flux should be, one may use the result of (1) in which a spatial derivative is taken of ((1)) i.e.

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \left(\sum_p p^3/2m f_p \exp(ipx) \right) / \left(\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx) \right) - KE(x) \left(\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx) \right) / \left(\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx) \right) = -d/dx V(x) \quad ((3))$$

Thus, one can see a microscopic form of force. Setting $x=0$, one obtains:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \left(\sum_p p^3/2m f_p \right) / \left(\sum_p f_p \right) - KE(x) \left(\sum_p f_p \right) / \left(\sum_p f_p \right) = -d/dx V(x) \quad ((4))$$

One may multiply ((4)) by dx to obtain work or the change in kinetic energy. One may also replace exp(ipx) with sin(px) or cos(px) to obtain a desired symmetry. This is useful if one is concerned with the 'i' which appears in $\exp(ipdx) = 1 + ip dx$. ((5))

The question arises whether ((4)) has any physical meaning i.e. could it be derived from first principles without resorting to taking the derivative of ((1)) and then setting x=0? In this note, we argue that this should be possible. It seems the LHS of ((4)) represents a kind of kinetic energy flux. If one has a kinetic energy of ((2)) at x, and one knows it is changing, somehow extra kinetic energy must be carried from x to dx in addition to KE(x=0). The expression in ((4)) is equivalent to:

$$\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} f_p / (\sum_p f_p) - (\sum_p p f_p) / (\sum_p f_p) dx \quad ((5))$$

Here we have multiplied by dx to obtain a change in energy.

((5)) has the appearance of a kind of kinetic energy flux. There is an average flow of momentum $(\sum_p p f_p) / (\sum_p f_p)$, but p may be greater than or less than this flow and carry extra positive or negative kinetic energy into the region dx A where A is a unit area. If ((5)) is nonzero, it seems one may achieve more or less kinetic energy at x=dx than at x=0. ((5)), however, must be ultimately equivalent to the weights f(p,x) changing with x because there is a force which ultimately changes the distribution at x=0 and x=dx. Otherwise, one would have the same kinetic energy for all x which is not the case.

The next task is to try to determine the general form of f(p,x) from ((2)). Imagine fp in ((2)) replaced with f(p,x) and a Taylor series taken with x=0 to obtain ((4)). In ((4)), one notices the form pfp. This is obtainable from $f_p \cos(px)$ because taking d/dx yields $p f_p$ with $\cos(0)=1$. One has two terms on the LHS of ((4)). This may be accounted for by considering a numerator and a denominator with the denominator $1/(b+cdx)$ becoming $b/c(1-dx)$. Thus, a form which matches ((4)) is:

$$KE(x) = \frac{1}{2m} (\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} f_p \cos(px)) / (\sum_p f_p \cos(px)) \quad ((6))$$

To be more general, one may replace cos(px) with exp(ipx) and ultimately obtain:

$$KE(x) = \frac{1}{2m} (\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} f_p \exp(ipx)) / (\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)) \quad ((7))$$

Thus, the mathematical form exp(ipx) appears as part of the weight f(p,x) making it a periodic, complex weight which is very different from the normal positive, real weights of regular probability theory. In fact, the probability weight seems to be:

$$P(p/x) = f_p \exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad \text{where } W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$$

One may consider the above in a different manner as dx appears in ((5)). Thus, jumping to cos(px) may seem like too rapid a jump. Nevertheless one has pfpdx in ((4)) as the 'change of the KE portion'. Thus, one has $f_p(1+pd x)$ overall. This factor appears over and over as one moves from one x point to the next one dx over. Thus, one obtains $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} (1+x/N)^N$ which is exp(px). Actually one should use ip to obtain exp(ipx).

Either way, it seems an $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with each p momentum state. This $\exp(ipx)$ emerges from the above arguments and is not used as a starting point, if one accepts the argument of kinetic energy flux increasing kinetic energy from one x point to another.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to discuss quantum bound states by considering an average kinetic energy at $x=0$ and trying to argue that kinetic energy increases as one moves to dx by $\sum \frac{p^2}{2m} f_p / (\sum f_p) - (\sum p f_p) / (\sum f_p) dx$. This seems to have the appearance of a kind of flux and one may argue that the expression could be written from first principles. From this one may deduce that $f(p,x)$ the weight of momentum p is $f_p \exp(ipx)$. Thus, there seems to be an $\exp(ipx)$ associated with a quantum particle in the state. Thus, both $\exp(ipx)$ and the wavefunction $= \sum f_p \exp(ipx)$ emerge from arguments about kinetic energy flux rather than appearing at the starting point of a quantum theory.

References

Ruggeri, Francesco R. Fluxes in Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2019)